

ROTA-BAXTER OPERATORI

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Annotatsiya: Trival bo‘lmagan ikki o‘lchovli algebralarning bazi klasslari uchun Rota-Baxter operatori va Rota-Baxter operatorini matrisa ko‘rinishi,

Kalit so‘zlar: ikki o‘lchovli algebralar, operator, struktura konstantalar.

OPERATOR ROTA-BAXTER

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Annotation: Matrix representation of Rota-Baxter operator and Rota-Baxter operator for some classes of non-trivial two-dimensional algebras

Key words: Two-dimensional algebras, operator, structure constants.

Rota-Baxter algebra is an algebra A over a field K with a linear endomorfism $\beta: A \rightarrow A$ satisfying the Rota-Baxter relation
$$\beta(e_i)\beta(e_j) = \beta(\beta(e_i)e_j + e_i\beta(e_j)) + a\beta(e_ie_j), i, j = \overline{1,2}$$
 where a is a fixed element of K .

The map β is called a Rota-Baxter operator of weight a . Associative Rota-Baxter algebras arise in many mathematical contexts, i.e., in integral and finite differences calculus, but also in perturbative renormalization in quantum field theory and many more see [1].

Over an algebraically closed field $F(\text{Char}(F) \neq 2 \text{ and } 3)$, any non-trivial 2-dimensional algebra is isomorphic to only one of the following algebras listed by their matrices of structure constants [2].

Problem: Here we would like to ask the following issue: If any non-trivial 2-dimensional algebra will be isomorphic A_{11} , in that case, is it possible to find the view of the a Rota-Baxter operator ?

If we use the matrix form of the operator Rota-Baxter, then for the eleven class:

$$A_{11} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

We are find following:

$$\begin{aligned} e_1 e_1 &= 0e_1 + 1e_2, e_1 e_2 = 1e_1 + 0e_2, \\ e_2 e_1 &= 1e_1 + 0e_2, e_2 e_2 = 0e_1 - 1e_2 \end{aligned}$$

We know that:

$$\begin{aligned} \beta(e_1) &= \begin{pmatrix} x & y \\ z & t \end{pmatrix} * \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = xe_1 + ze_2 \\ \beta(e_2) &= \begin{pmatrix} x & y \\ z & t \end{pmatrix} * \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = ye_1 + te_2 \end{aligned}$$

We construct the following system of equations taking into account $i, j = \overline{1,2}$ and the left and right sides of equation:

$$\begin{cases} 2xy + ay = 0 \\ x^2 + z^2 - 2xt - at = 0 \\ x^2 + y^2 - 2yz + ax = 0 \\ xy - xz - yt - zt - az = 0 \\ 4yt - 2xy + ay = 0 \\ y^2 + t^2 - 2yz + at = 0 \end{cases}$$

Taking into account the system solutions, we divide the solutions into the following cases:

Case 1: If the condition $2x + a \neq 0$ and $x = 0$ holds, then the solutions:

$$x = y = t = z = 0$$

Rota-Baxter operator view will be as follows:

$$\beta = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

here $a \neq 0$.

Case 2: If the condition $2x + a \neq 0, x = -a$ holds, then the solutions:

$$x = -a, y = 0, t = -a, z = 0.$$

Rota-Baxter operator view will be as follows:

$$\beta = \begin{pmatrix} -a & 0 \\ 0 & -a \end{pmatrix}$$

here $a \neq 0$.

In conclusion, we arrive at the following theorem:

Theorem-1. If any non-trivial 2-dimensional algebra will be isomorphic A_{11} , in that case The matrix form of the β -Rota-Baxter operator can be found.

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